

On Polymorphic Attacks in $ASPIC^+$

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Abstract. A polymorphic attack is a peculiar situation where there are multiple reasons, of different nature, for an argument to attack another argument. In this paper we analyse the possible occurrence of polymorphic attacks in the context of the $ASPIC^+$ formalism, pointing out that they are not just a technical artifact but can occur in some practical reasoning context. While in $ASPIC^+$ polymorphic attacks are dealt with in an implicit and fixed way, we propose a tunable approach to their treatment, based on the novel notion of defeat generation function. In particular, we introduce a property of faithfulness for this function and prove that it guarantees the satisfaction of the rationality postulates proposed by Caminada and Amgoud, showing that a greater flexibility in the treatment of polymorphic attacks can be achieved without affecting the technical soundness of the formalism.

Keywords. Structured argumentation; Polymorphic attacks; Argumentation frameworks

1. Introduction

$ASPIC^+$ [5] is a formalism for structured argumentation, featuring remarkable expressiveness properties, which include an articulated classification of attacks in three types (undercutting, rebutting, and undermining). For each type of attack to occur, some conditions are identified, e.g. rebut happens when the conclusion of an argument is a contrary of the conclusion of another one, while in the case of undercut contrariness involves the name of a defeasible rule. Given two arguments α and β , it may be the case that several of the conditions determining the existence of an attack from α to β hold at the same time, e.g. it can occur that α rebuts and undercuts β at the same time: in such a situation we say that there is a *polymorphic* attack from α to β . As to our knowledge, this phenomenon has not been previously considered in the literature and has only been preliminarily analyzed in [2]. In this paper, after recalling some notions and examples on polymorphic attacks from [2], we make a step forward concerning their technical treatment. In particular, given that in $ASPIC^+$ the attack relation is the basis for the construction of an argumentation framework used to assess the acceptability of arguments, we introduce the notion of defeat generation function (DGF), thus encompassing alternative options for the construction process mentioned above. We then define a property of faithfulness for DGFs and show that any faithful DGF guarantees the satisfaction of the rationality postulates of [3]. This proves that a greater flexibility in the treatment of polymorphic attacks can be achieved without affecting the technical soundness of the formalism. The paper is organised as follows. After recalling background notions in Section 2, we discuss

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and exemplify polymorphic attacks in Section 3. Section 4 proposes the notion of defeat generation function and proves that compliance with rationality postulates is guaranteed if this function satisfies a property of faithfulness. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. Background

First, we briefly recall Dung's theory of argumentation frameworks [4].

Definition 1. An argumentation framework (AF) is a pair $\mathcal{F} = \langle A, \rightarrow \rangle$, where A is a set of arguments and $\rightarrow \subseteq (A \times A)$ is a binary relation on A .

When $(\alpha, \beta) \in \rightarrow$ (also denoted as $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$) we say that α attacks β . For a set $X \subseteq A$ and an argument $\alpha \in A$ we write $\alpha \rightarrow X$ if $\exists \beta \in X : \alpha \rightarrow \beta$ and $X \rightarrow \alpha$ if $\exists \beta \in X : \beta \rightarrow \alpha$, and we denote the arguments attacking X as $X^- \triangleq \{\alpha \in A \mid \alpha \rightarrow X\}$ and those attacked by X as $X^+ \triangleq \{\alpha \in A \mid X \rightarrow \alpha\}$. An *extension-based* semantics σ specifies the criteria for identifying, for a generic AF, a set of *extensions*, namely sets of arguments considered to be acceptable together. Given a semantics σ , the set of extensions prescribed by σ for an AF \mathcal{F} is denoted as $\mathcal{E}_\sigma(\mathcal{F})$. Several semantics are recalled in Definition 2, along with some underlying notions. For more details, the reader is referred to [1].

Definition 2. Let $\mathcal{F} = \langle A, \rightarrow \rangle$ be an AF, $\alpha \in A$ and $X \subseteq A$. X is conflict-free, denoted as $X \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F})$, iff $X \cap X^- = \emptyset$. α is acceptable with respect to X (or α is defended by X) iff $\{\alpha\}^- \subseteq X^+$. The function $F_{\mathcal{F}} : 2^A \rightarrow 2^A$ which, given a set $X \subseteq A$, returns the set of the acceptable arguments with respect to X , is called the characteristic function of \mathcal{F} . X is admissible (denoted as $X \in \mathcal{E}_{AD}(\mathcal{F})$) iff $X \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F})$ and $X \subseteq F_{\mathcal{F}}(X)$. X is a complete extension (denoted as $X \in \mathcal{E}_{CO}(\mathcal{F})$) iff $X \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F})$ and $X = F_{\mathcal{F}}(X)$. X is the grounded extension (denoted as $X = GR(\mathcal{F})$ or $X \in \mathcal{E}_{GR}(\mathcal{F})$) iff X is the least fixed point of $F_{\mathcal{F}}$ (equivalently, the least complete extension of \mathcal{F}). X is a preferred extension (denoted as $X \in \mathcal{E}_{PR}(\mathcal{F})$) iff X is a maximal (with respect to set inclusion) admissible set. X is a stable extension (denoted as $X \in \mathcal{E}_{ST}(\mathcal{F})$) iff $X^+ = A \setminus X$. X is a semi-stable extension (denoted as $X \in \mathcal{E}_{SST}(\mathcal{F})$) iff it is a complete extension such that $X \cup X^+$ is maximal (wrt \subseteq) among all complete extensions.

We recall in the sequel the essentials of the definition of $ASPIC^+$ [5].

Definition 3. An argumentation system is a tuple $AS = (\mathcal{L}, \bar{\cdot}, \mathcal{R}, n)$ where:

1. \mathcal{L} is a logical language
2. $\bar{\cdot}$ is a contrariness function from \mathcal{L} to $2^{\mathcal{L}}$ such that: (i) ϕ is a contrary of ψ if $\phi \in \bar{\psi}$, $\psi \notin \bar{\phi}$; (ii) ϕ is a contradictory of ψ (denoted by $\phi = -\psi$) if $\phi \in \bar{\psi}$, $\psi \in \bar{\phi}$; (iii) each $\phi \in \mathcal{L}$ has at least one contradictory
3. $\mathcal{R} = (\mathcal{R}_S, \mathcal{R}_D)$ is a pair of sets of strict (\mathcal{R}_S) and defeasible (\mathcal{R}_D) inference rules of the form $\phi_1, \dots, \phi_n \rightarrow \phi$ and $\phi_1, \dots, \phi_n \Rightarrow \phi$ respectively (where ϕ_i, ϕ are meta-variables ranging over wff in \mathcal{L}), and $\mathcal{R}_S \cap \mathcal{R}_D = \emptyset$
4. $n : \mathcal{R}_D \rightarrow \mathcal{L}$ is a naming convention for \mathcal{R}_D .

Given a rule $r = \phi_1, \dots, \phi_n \rightarrow (\Rightarrow)\phi$, ϕ is the consequent of the rule, denoted as $cons(r)$, and $\{\phi_1, \dots, \phi_n\}$ is the set of the antecedents of the rule, denoted as $ant(r)$ (note that $ant(r) \neq \emptyset$ since $n \geq 1$).

Two notions of *consistency* are considered in $ASPIC^+$.

Definition 4. For any $S \subseteq \mathcal{L}$, let the closure of S under strict rules, denoted $Cl_{\mathcal{R}_S}(S)$, be the smallest set containing S and the consequent of any strict rule in \mathcal{R}_S , whose antecedents are in $Cl_{\mathcal{R}_S}(S)$. Then a set $S \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ is: (i) directly consistent iff $\nexists \varphi, \psi \in S$ such that $\varphi \in \overline{\psi}$; (ii) indirectly consistent iff $Cl_{\mathcal{R}_S}(S)$ is directly consistent.

A knowledge base is a subset of \mathcal{L} including certain (called *axioms*) and defeasible (called *ordinary*) premises. It gives rise to the notion of argumentation theory, where arguments are built from a knowledge base using rules.

Definition 5. A knowledge base in an argumentation system $AS = (\mathcal{L}, \overline{\cdot}, \mathcal{R}, n)$ is a set $\mathcal{K} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ consisting of two disjoint subsets \mathcal{K}_n (the axioms) and \mathcal{K}_p (the ordinary premises). The tuple $AT = (AS, \mathcal{K})$ is called an argumentation theory.

Definition 6. An argument α on the basis of a knowledge base \mathcal{K} in an argumentation system $(\mathcal{L}, \overline{\cdot}, \mathcal{R}, n)$ is:

1. φ if $\varphi \in \mathcal{K}$ with: $Prem(\alpha) = \{\varphi\}$; $Conc(\alpha) = \varphi$; $Sub(\alpha) = \{\varphi\}$; $Rules(\alpha) = \emptyset$; $Top(\alpha) = \text{undefined}$.
2. $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n \rightarrow (\Rightarrow) \psi$ if $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$ are arguments such that there exists a strict (defeasible) rule $Conc(\alpha_1), \dots, Conc(\alpha_n) \rightarrow (\Rightarrow) \psi$ in \mathcal{R}_S (\mathcal{R}_D) with: $Prem(\alpha) = Prem(\alpha_1) \cup \dots \cup Prem(\alpha_n)$; $Conc(\alpha) = \psi$; $Sub(\alpha) = Sub(\alpha_1) \cup \dots \cup Sub(\alpha_n) \cup \{\alpha\}$; $Rules(\alpha) = Rules(\alpha_1) \cup \dots \cup Rules(\alpha_n) \cup \{Conc(\alpha_1), \dots, Conc(\alpha_n) \rightarrow (\Rightarrow) \psi\}$; $Top(\alpha) = Conc(\alpha_1), \dots, Conc(\alpha_n) \rightarrow (\Rightarrow) \psi$; $DefRules(\alpha) = \{r \mid r \in Rules(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{R}_D\}$; $StRules(\alpha) = \{r \mid r \in Rules(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{R}_S\}$.

For any argument α , $Prem_n(\alpha) = Prem(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{K}_n$; $Prem_p(\alpha) = Prem(\alpha) \cap \mathcal{K}_p$. α is: strict if $DefRules(\alpha) = \emptyset$, defeasible if $DefRules(\alpha) \neq \emptyset$; firm if $Prem_p(\alpha) = \emptyset$; plausible if $Prem_p(\alpha) \neq \emptyset$; finite if $Rules(\alpha)$ is finite.

We assume, as in [5], that the set $Prem(\alpha)$ is always finite. An argument may include both fallible (ordinary premises and defeasible rules) and infallible (axioms and strict rules) elements. Definition 7 is based on this distinction.

Definition 7. For any set of arguments $\{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ the argument α is a strict continuation of $\{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ iff $Prem_p(\alpha) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n Prem_p(\alpha_i)$; $DefRules(\alpha) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n DefRules(\alpha_i)$; $StRules(\alpha) \supseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^n StRules(\alpha_i)$; $Prem_n(\alpha) \supseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^n Prem_n(\alpha_i)$.

Notation 1. Some further notations are useful. Given $S \subseteq \mathcal{L}$, $S \vdash \varphi$ denotes that there exists a strict argument α such that $Conc(\alpha) = \varphi$, with $Prem(\alpha) \subseteq S$. Given an argumentation theory $AT = (AS, \mathcal{K})$, the set of all finite arguments constructed from \mathcal{K} in AS , called the set of arguments on the basis of AT , is denoted as $Args(AT)$.

A special role will be played by the subarguments which intuitively represent the ‘last defeasible’ elements in the construction of an argument.

Definition 8. Given an argument α the set $M(\alpha)$ of the maximal fallible subarguments of α is defined such that for any $\alpha' \in Sub(\alpha)$, $\alpha' \in M(\alpha)$ iff: i) α' is an ordinary premise or has a defeasible top rule; ii) there is no $\alpha'' \in Sub(\alpha)$ such that $\alpha'' \neq \alpha'$ and $\alpha' \in Sub(\alpha'')$ and α'' satisfies i).

The notion of *c-consistency* is based on contradiction.

Definition 9. A set $S \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ is c-consistent if for no φ it holds that $S \vdash \varphi, -\varphi$. Otherwise S is c-inconsistent. S is minimally c-inconsistent iff S is c-inconsistent and $\forall S' \subsetneq S$, S' is c-consistent. An argument α on the basis of a knowledge-base \mathcal{K} in an argumentation system $(\mathcal{L}, \bar{\cdot}, \mathcal{R}, n)$ is c-consistent iff $\text{Prem}(\alpha)$ is c-consistent.

Accordingly, several properties for an argumentation theory can be formulated.

Definition 10. Let $AT = (AS, \mathcal{K})$ be an argumentation theory, where $AS = (\mathcal{L}, \bar{\cdot}, \mathcal{R}, n)$. AT is: i) closed under contraposition iff for all $S \subseteq \mathcal{L}$, $\psi \in S$, $\varphi \in \mathcal{L}$, if $S \vdash \varphi$ then $S \setminus \{\psi\} \cup \{-\varphi\} \vdash -\psi$; ii) closed under transposition iff if $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_n \rightarrow \psi \in \mathcal{R}_S$ then, for $i = 1 \dots n$, $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_{i-1}, -\psi, \varphi_{i+1}, \dots, \varphi_n \rightarrow -\varphi_i \in \mathcal{R}_S$; iii) axiom consistent iff $Cl_{\mathcal{R}_S}(\mathcal{K}_n)$ is directly consistent; iv) c-classical iff for any minimal c-inconsistent $S \subseteq \mathcal{L}$ and for any $\varphi \in S$, it holds that $S \setminus \{\varphi\} \vdash -\varphi$; v) well-formed if whenever φ is a contrary of ψ then $\psi \notin \mathcal{K}_n$ and ψ is not the consequent of a strict rule.

Three kinds of attack between arguments are considered.

Definition 11. An argument α attacks an argument β iff α undercuts, rebuts, or undermines β where: α undercuts β (on β') iff $\text{Conc}(\alpha) \in n(r)$ for some $\beta' \in \text{Sub}(\beta)$ such that $r = \text{Top}(\beta')$ is defeasible. α rebuts β (on β') iff $\text{Conc}(\alpha) \in \bar{\varphi}$ for some $\beta' \in \text{Sub}(\beta)$ of the form $\beta''_1, \dots, \beta''_n \Rightarrow \varphi$. In such a case α contrary-rebuts β iff $\text{Conc}(\alpha)$ is a contrary of φ . α undermines β (on β') iff $\text{Conc}(\alpha) \in \bar{\varphi}$ for some $\beta' = \varphi$, $\varphi \in \text{Prem}_p(\beta)$. In such a case α contrary-undermines β iff $\text{Conc}(\alpha)$ is a contrary of φ .

In some cases, attack effectiveness depends on a preference ordering \preceq over arguments (assumed to be a preorder following [6]). As usual $\alpha \prec \beta$ iff $\alpha \preceq \beta$ and $\beta \not\preceq \alpha$.

Definition 12. An argument ordering \preceq is reasonable iff: i) $\forall \alpha, \beta$ if α is strict and firm and β is plausible or defeasible, then $\beta \prec \alpha$; ii) $\forall \alpha, \beta$ if α is strict and firm then $\alpha \not\prec \beta$; iii) $\forall \alpha, \alpha', \beta$ with α' a strict continuation of $\{\alpha\}$, if $\alpha \not\prec \beta$ then $\alpha' \not\prec \beta$ and if $\beta \not\prec \alpha$ then $\beta \not\prec \alpha'$ iv) let $\top_A = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ be a finite set of arguments and for $i = 1 \dots n$ let α^{+i} be some strict continuation of $\top_A \setminus \{\alpha_i\}$. Then, it is not the case that $\forall i \alpha^{+i} \prec \alpha_i$.

Effective attacks give rise to defeat.

Definition 13. Let α attack β on β' . If α undercuts, contrary-rebuts, or contrary-undermines β on β' , then α preference-independent attacks β on β' , otherwise α preference-dependent attacks β on β' . α defeats β iff for some β' either α preference-independent attacks β on β' or α preference-dependent attacks β on β' and $\alpha \not\prec \beta'$.

Two kinds of structured argumentation frameworks are defined from an argumentation theory, using the attack relation.

Definition 14. Let $AT = (AS, \mathcal{K})$ be an argumentation theory. A (c-)structured argumentation framework, denoted as (c-)SAF, defined by AT is a triple (S_A, C, \preceq) where S_A is the set of all (c-consistent) finite arguments constructed from \mathcal{K} in AS (henceforth called the set of arguments on the basis of AT), $C \subseteq S_A \times S_A$ is such that $(\alpha, \beta) \in C$ iff α attacks β , and \preceq is an ordering on S_A .

Well-definedness of (c-)structured argumentation frameworks depends on the properties of the underlying theory.

Definition 15. A SAF defined by an AT is well-defined iff AT is *c-classical*, axiom consistent, well-formed and closed under contraposition or closed under transposition. A *c-SAF* defined by an AT is well-defined iff AT is axiom consistent, well-formed and closed under contraposition or closed under transposition.

A traditional Dung's framework is derived from a (*c*-)SAF using the defeat relation.

Definition 16. Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a (*c*-)SAF, and $D \subseteq S_A \times S_A$ be the defeat relation according to Def. 13. The argumentation framework corresponding to Δ is defined as $\mathcal{F}_\Delta = (S_A, D)$.

Compliance with the rationality postulates of closure and (direct and indirect) consistency introduced in [3] is proved in [5] under the assumptions above.

Theorem 1. Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a well-defined (*c*-)SAF with reasonable \preceq and E a complete extension of \mathcal{F}_Δ . Then i) $\forall \alpha \in E$ if $\alpha' \in \text{Sub}(\alpha)$ then $\alpha' \in E$; ii) $\{\text{Conc}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in E\} = \text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}_S}(\{\text{Conc}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in E\})$; iii) $\{\text{Conc}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in E\}$ is consistent; iv) $\text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}_S}(\{\text{Conc}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in E\})$ is consistent.

3. Polymorphic attacks in ASPIC⁺

In ASPIC⁺ the potential occurrence of an attack between two arguments (Definition 11) depends essentially on a relation of contrariness between the conclusion of the attacking argument and an attackable element of (a subargument of) the attacked argument.

Three types of attack (undercut, rebut, and undermining) are identified, depending on the attackable element involved. Moreover, rebutting and undermining attacks are partitioned into two subclasses, depending on whether the relevant contrariness relation is symmetric or asymmetric.

It is worth noting that Definition 11 does not entail that the three types of attack are mutually exclusive: in specific situations, more than one of the conditions establishing the occurrence of an attack may hold at the same time for the same pair of arguments α and β . To exemplify, in order to have that α undercuts and rebuts β at the same time, the conclusion of α should be a contrary both of a conclusion of a subargument of β and of the name of a defeasible rule used in a subargument of β , as shown in Example 1.

Example 1. Let $AS_1 = (\mathcal{L}, \bar{\cdot}, \mathcal{R}, n)$ such that: $\mathcal{L} = \{\varphi, \psi, \chi, \omega\}$; $\omega \in \bar{\psi}$; $\omega \in \bar{\chi}$; $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_D = \{r_1\}$ where $r_1 = \varphi \Rightarrow \psi$; $n(r_1) = \chi$. Consider then the following knowledge base in AS_1 : $\mathcal{K} = \mathcal{K}_p = \{\varphi, \omega\}$. We have then the following arguments: $\alpha_1 = \varphi$, $\alpha_2 = \omega$, $\alpha_3 = \alpha_1 \Rightarrow \psi$. It turns out that α_2 both rebuts and undercuts α_3 .

Examples where α undercuts and undermines β at the same time or α rebuts and undermines β at the same time can easily be built in a similar way (see [2]).

Moreover, as is probably already evident, it is also possible to have a situation where an argument attacks another argument in all three possible ways.

Example 2. Let $AS_2 = (\mathcal{L}, \bar{\cdot}, \mathcal{R}, n)$ which is a variation of AS_1 with the only difference that $\omega \in \bar{\varphi}$ in addition to $\omega \in \bar{\psi}$ and $\omega \in \bar{\chi}$. Consider then the same knowledge base: $\mathcal{K} = \mathcal{K}_p = \{\varphi, \omega\}$. We have, similarly to above, the following arguments: $\alpha_1 = \varphi$, $\alpha_2 = \omega$, $\alpha_3 = \alpha_1 \Rightarrow \psi$. It turns out that α_2 undermines, rebuts, and undercuts α_3 .

In the examples above, there is a language element that belongs to the contrariness function of at least two other elements. One may wonder whether this is a necessary condition for *polymorphic* attacks to occur in $ASPIC^+$, or *polymorphic* attacks may occur even under the constraint that each language element belongs to at most one contrariness function. The latter is true, though rather peculiar situations must be considered, as shown by the following example.

Example 3. Let $AS_3 = (\mathcal{L}, \bar{\cdot}, \mathcal{R}, n)$ such that: $\mathcal{L} = \{\varphi, \psi, \chi, \omega\}$; $\omega \in \bar{\chi}$; $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_D = \{r_1\}$ where $r_1 = \varphi, \chi \Rightarrow \psi$; $n(r_1) = \chi$. Consider then the following knowledge base in AS_3 : $\mathcal{K} = \mathcal{K}_p = \{\varphi, \chi, \omega\}$. We have then the following arguments: $\alpha_1 = \varphi$, $\alpha_2 = \omega$, $\alpha_3 = \chi$, $\alpha_4 = \alpha_1, \alpha_3 \Rightarrow \psi$. It turns out that α_2 both undermines and undercuts α_4 .

For the sake of brevity and simplicity, the examples presented above are rather compact. More articulated examples, in particular involving longer rule chains, can easily be generated. Thus, it emerges that a variety of polymorphic attacks are actually possible.

Two main questions then arise. On the application side, one may wonder whether polymorphic attacks may occur in practice, i.e., whether there are realistic reasoning contexts giving rise to them. On the technical side, one has, in any case, to consider whether they are problematic in any sense and whether they require a suitable treatment.

As to the first question, consider the following situation. Suppose you have a defeasible rule r_1 stating that people wearing overalls are usually workers, and another defeasible rule r_2 stating that workers are typically adults. Moreover you know that r_1 is not applicable to children (since they may wear overalls in masquerade or for other fun reasons) and that children are not adults. Now you have a picture including a person who seems to be wearing overalls and to be a child: being a child is both a rebut and an undercut for the argument that the person is an adult, as shown in the example below.

Example 4. Let $AS_w = (\mathcal{L}, \bar{\cdot}, \mathcal{R}, n)$ be defined as follows. $\mathcal{L} = \{Wo, Wk, Ch, Ad, N_1, N_2\}$ where *Wo* means wears overalls, *Wk* means is a worker, *Ch* means is a child, *Ad* means is an adult, and N_1 and N_2 are symbols used for rule names. Then we assume $Ch \in \bar{Ad}$, $Ad \in \bar{Ch}$ and $Ch \in \bar{N}_1$. We consider a set of two defeasible rules: $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_D = \{r_1, r_2\}$ where $r_1 = Wo \Rightarrow Wk$ with $n(r_1) = N_1$ and $r_2 = Wk \Rightarrow Ad$ with $n(r_2) = N_2$. We assume the following knowledge base in AS_w : $\mathcal{K} = \mathcal{K}_p = \{Wo, Ch\}$. We have then the following arguments: $\alpha_1 = Wo$, $\alpha_2 = Ch$, $\alpha_3 = \alpha_1 \Rightarrow Wk$, $\alpha_4 = \alpha_3 \Rightarrow Ad$. It emerges that α_2 undercuts α_3 and then α_2 both rebuts α_4 (on α_4) and undercuts α_4 (on α_3). Moreover α_4 undermines α_2 .

Example 4 provides an instance of polymorphic attack (rebut and undercut) arising from a realistic reasoning situation. While a systematic analysis of realistic examples giving rise to other combinations of types of attack is left to future work, we suggest that Example 4 is sufficient to show that polymorphic attacks are more than a formal curiosity and should not be overlooked. We turn, therefore, to consider the questions raised by polymorphic attacks from a technical and conceptual perspective.

Starting from the technical side, we remark first that Definition 11 is agnostic with respect to polymorphic attacks: it says that an argument α attacks an argument β iff α undercuts, rebuts, or undermines β , and does not explicitly assume nor implicitly relies on the fact that the disjunction is exclusive.

Definition 13 then distinguishes preference-dependent and preference-independent attacks from an argument α to an argument β with reference to the subargument β' to

which the attack is directed. It turns out that an argument α can attack another argument β in a preference-dependent and in a preference-independent way at the same time. For instance, in Example 4, α_2 preference-dependent attacks α_4 on α_4 and preference-independent attacks α_4 on α_3 .

While this is a bit peculiar, it is, *per se*, not problematic for the notion of defeat introduced in Definition 13. It states that an argument α defeats an argument β if there is some $\beta' \in \text{Sub}(\beta)$ on which the attack is successful. As previously discussed, it may happen that: (i) there can be several such subarguments β' and (ii) preferences may or may not play a role for the success of different attacks. However the facts (i) and (ii) do not represent a problem: there will in any case a single defeat from α to β (possibly corresponding to more than one attack).

The defeat relation is then the basis for the construction of the argumentation framework in Definition 16, on which the assessment of the acceptability of arguments is based. Thus, technically speaking, polymorphic attacks do not pose problems to the relevant definitions in $ASPIC^+$.

We argue, however, that from the conceptual point of view, some issues arise. As remarked above, Definition 13 admits that an argument α can both preference-independent and preference-dependent attack another argument.

Let us refer to Example 4. The undercutting attacks from α_2 to α_3 and from α_2 to α_4 (on α_3) are preference-independent, while the rebutting attacks from α_2 to α_4 and vice versa are preference-dependent. According to Definition 13, α_2 then defeats both α_3 and α_4 independently of any preference, while α_4 defeats α_2 only if $\alpha_4 \not\prec \alpha_2$. Assuming $\alpha_4 \not\prec \alpha_2$, we get that in the argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_w prescribed by Definition 16 for Example 4 (see Figure 1) there is a formally symmetric defeat between α_4 and α_2 whose branches are however conceptually asymmetric: one branch has a polymorphic origin, while the other arises from a rebutting attack.

Let us examine the outcomes of the evaluation of the arguments in \mathcal{F}_w according to standard semantics. The grounded extension consists of the unique unattacked argument α_1 ($GR(\mathcal{F}_w) = \{\alpha_1\}$), while in the case of preferred, stable, and semi-stable semantics, we have two extensions: $\mathcal{E}_{PR}(\mathcal{F}_w) = \mathcal{E}_{ST}(\mathcal{F}_w) = \mathcal{E}_{SST}(\mathcal{F}_w) = \{\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2\}, \{\alpha_1, \alpha_3, \alpha_4\}\}$.

In words, α_1 is the only argument skeptically accepted with any semantics, while α_2 (namely the evidence that the person is a child) is regarded as dubious, due to the mutual attack with α_4 . It is interesting to note that α_4 defends its own subargument α_3 from the undercutting attack coming from α_2 . This is a bit peculiar: a consequence that the undercutting attack is meant to prevent to draw is used to rebut the source of the undercutting attack itself.

Whether this is conceptually legitimate or problematic can be regarded as a matter of discussion, which we leave to future work. In this paper, we limit ourselves to suggesting that further investigation on polymorphic attacks in $ASPIC^+$ is worth pursuing and that it may stimulate the study of alternative notions of defeat in $ASPIC^+$. In particular, one might consider a revision of the formalism where the fact that an attack whose source is an argument α gives rise to a successful defeat takes into account the possible existence of polymorphic attacks. In particular, polymorphic attacks involving proper subarguments of α , might, in a sense, override the self-defence capability of α against them. To allow this kind of options we propose a revision of $ASPIC^+$ encompassing a tunable notion of defeat.

Figure 1. The argumentation framework \mathcal{F}_w corresponding to Example 4.

4. A tunable notion of defeat relation

To allow different ways of building the defeat relation when polymorphic attacks are present, we need first of all to introduce a notion of potential defeat: the following definition is meant to replace Definition 13.

Definition 17. Let α attack β on β' . If α undercuts, contrary-rebut, or contrary-undermines β on β' , then α preference-independent attacks β on β' , otherwise α preference-dependent attacks β on β' . Then, α potentially defeats β iff for some β' α preference-independent attacks β on β' or α preference-dependent attacks β on β' and $\alpha \not\prec \beta'$.

When α potentially defeats β , there is at least a four-tuple $\langle \alpha, \beta, \beta', T \rangle$, where α, β, β' satisfy the conditions of Definition 17, while $T \in \mathbb{TS} = \{UC, SR, SM, CR, CM\}$, where \mathbb{TS} is the set of attack types and its elements correspond to undercut (UC), non-contrary (i.e. symmetric) rebut (SR), non-contrary undermining (SM), contrary-rebut (CR) and contrary-undermining (CM).

Given an argumentation theory AT , we denote as PDS_{AT} the set of all four-tuples respecting the conditions established by Definition 17. For arguments α and β , we define $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \triangleq \{\langle \gamma, \delta, \delta', T \rangle \in PDS_{AT} \mid \gamma = \alpha \text{ and } \delta = \beta\}$.

We keep unchanged Definitions 14 and 15 and then introduce the notion of defeat generation function.

A defeat generation function for an argumentation theory AT is a function $DGF_{AT} : S_A \times S_A \rightarrow \{T, F\}$ which, given a pair of arguments α and β , returns T iff α defeats β , F otherwise. Using this notion we modify Definition 16 as follows.

Definition 18. Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a (c -)SAF, and let DGF_{AT} be a defeat generation function. The argumentation framework corresponding to Δ according to DGF_{AT} is defined as $\mathcal{F}_\Delta^{DGF} = (S_A, D)$ where $D = \{(\alpha, \beta) \in S_A \times S_A \mid DGF_{AT}(\alpha, \beta) = T\}$.

Definition 18 enables the possibility of alternative defeat relations depending on the defeat generation function adopted. First it can be noted that the original $ASPIC^+$ formalism corresponds to the use of the following defeat generation function:

$DGF_{AT}(\alpha, \beta) = T$ iff $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$.

In words, every potential defeat becomes a defeat. We are interested in considering other choices for DGF_{AT} , which are still able to ensure the satisfaction of the rationality postulates. To this purpose we introduce the notion of *faithful* defeat generation function.

Definition 19. A defeat generation function DGF_{AT} for an argumentation theory AT is *faithful* if the following conditions hold for every pair of arguments α and β :

- if $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) = \emptyset$ then $DGF_{AT}(\alpha, \beta) = F$;
- if $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$ and $PDS_{AT}(\beta \rightarrow \alpha) = \emptyset$ then $DGF_{AT}(\alpha, \beta) = T$;

- if $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$ and $PDS_{AT}(\beta \rightarrow \alpha) \neq \emptyset$ then $DGF_{AT}(\alpha, \beta) = T$ or $DGF_{AT}(\beta, \alpha) = T$.

The main difference with respect to $ASPIC^+$ is represented by the third condition: in case there are two potential defeats between two distinct arguments it is possible (according to some criterion) to ignore one of the two potential defeats and have a unidirectional defeat. For instance, if α rebuts β while β undercuts α it is possible to give priority to one of the two types of attack, while ignoring the other.

The question is now whether this more liberal notion of defeat is still compliant with rationality postulates.

We show that the answer is positive by adapting the line of proof used in sections 4.1 and 4.2 of [5] to the more flexible formal context we propose, commenting the adaptation and the differences. Note that in the following we will always assume a faithful defeat generation function DGF_{AT} and the relevant argumentation framework $\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF}$.

To begin, it is worth recalling that the line of proof of [5] uses the notions of attack-based conflict freeness and of defeat-based acceptability. This means that the property of conflict-freeness for a set S of arguments refers to the fact that there are no $\alpha, \beta \in S$ such that α attacks β according to Definition 11. To avoid confusion with conflict-freeness in Definition 2 we will say that a set is att-conflict-free if it satisfies this property.

As a consequence, the notion of admissible set has a share of both the attack-based and the defeat-based perspective: a set S is admissible in $\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF}$ iff S is att-conflict-free and every $\alpha \in S$ is acceptable with respect to S according to Definition 2. Then also other semantics notions inherit the twofold perspective, since they are based on conflict-freeness and admissibility.

Lemma 1 clarifies a basic relation between the two notions of conflict-freeness .

Lemma 1. *If a set S is att-conflict-free then $S \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. If $S \notin \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$ then S is not att-conflict-free.*

Proof. As to the first statement, if S is att-conflict-free, for every $\alpha, \beta \in S$ it holds that $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) = PDS_{AT}(\beta \rightarrow \alpha) = \emptyset$ and then from faithfulness it follows $(\alpha, \beta) \notin D$. The second statement follow obviously from the first one. \square

Having clarified this aspect, let us proceed with the proof line.

Proposition 1 adapts Proposition 8 of [5] (the difference is in the second statement: we prove the existence of a potential defeat while in [5] the proved relation is a defeat).

Proposition 1. *Let α and β be arguments, where β is plausible or defeasible and α and β have contradictory conclusions, and assume $Prem(\alpha) \cup Prem(\beta)$ is c-consistent if α and β are defined as in Definition 9. Then:*

1. For all $\beta' \in M(\beta)$ there exists a strict continuation $\alpha_{\beta'}^+$ of $(M(\beta) \setminus \{\beta'\}) \cup M(\alpha)$ such that $\alpha_{\beta'}^+$ rebuts or undermines β on β'
2. if $\beta \prec \alpha$ and \preceq is reasonable then for some $\beta' \in M(\beta)$ $PDS_{AT}(\alpha_{\beta'}^+ \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. As to the first statement, we observe that it is not affected by the modifications we introduced and the proof is the same as in [5]. As to the second statement, the proof in [5] shows, using the assumption that \preceq is reasonable, that there is $\beta' \in M(\beta)$ such that $\alpha_{\beta'}^+$ rebuts or undermines β on β' and $\alpha_{\beta'}^+ \not\prec \beta'$. This fact is not affected by our

modifications and entails that $\langle \alpha_{\beta'}^+, \beta, \beta', T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some attack type T , from which we get $PDS_{AT}(\alpha_{\beta'}^+ \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$. \square

Lemma 2 adapts Lemma 35 of [5].

Lemma 2. *Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a (c-)SAF, DGF_{AT} be a faithful defeat generation function with $\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF} = (S_A, D)$.*

1. *If $\alpha \in S_A$ is acceptable in $\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF}$ with respect to $S \subseteq S_A$ then α is acceptable with respect to any superset of S ;*
2. *If $(\alpha, \beta) \in D$ then $\{(\alpha, \beta'), (\beta', \alpha)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$ for some $\beta' \in Sub(\beta)$;*
3. *If $(\alpha, \beta') \in D$ and $\beta' \in Sub(\beta)$ then $\{(\alpha, \beta), (\beta, \alpha)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$;*
4. *If $\alpha \in S_A$ is acceptable in $\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF}$ with respect to $S \subseteq S_A$, and $\alpha' \in Sub(\alpha)$ then α' is acceptable with respect to $S \cup \{\alpha\}$.*

Proof. The first statement is a direct consequence of the definition of acceptability.

As to 2., on the basis of Definitions 18 and 19, $(\alpha, \beta) \in D$ implies $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$, namely $\exists \langle \alpha, \beta, \beta', T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some $\beta' \in Sub(\beta)$ and some attack type T . It follows that also $\langle \alpha, \beta', \beta', T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$, hence $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta') \neq \emptyset$ and from Definitions 18 and 19 we get $\{(\alpha, \beta'), (\beta', \alpha)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$.

As to 3., $(\alpha, \beta') \in D$ implies $\exists \langle \alpha, \beta', \beta'', T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some $\beta'' \in Sub(\beta)$ and some attack type T and, as above, it follows that $\langle \alpha, \beta'', \beta'', T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$. Obviously $\beta'' \in Sub(\beta)$ and it follows that $\langle \alpha, \beta, \beta'', T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$, entailing $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$ and from Definitions 18 and 19 we get $\{(\alpha, \beta), (\beta, \alpha)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$.

As to 4., consider any β such that $(\beta, \alpha') \in D$. From point 3 we get $\{(\alpha, \beta), (\beta, \alpha)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. We consider the two possible (and not mutually exclusive) cases. If $(\alpha, \beta) \in D$ clearly α defends α' from the attack of β . If $(\beta, \alpha) \in D$ then, by the acceptability of α there must be some $\gamma \in S$ such that $(\gamma, \beta) \in D$ and hence S defends α' from the attack of β . Combining the two conditions, it follows that $S \cup \{\alpha\}$ defends α' . \square

Comparing with Lemma 35 of [5]: item 1 is the same; in items 2. and 3. we derive the existence of at least one in a pair of mutual defeats, while in [5] the existence of a specific defeat is obtained; in the fourth statement, we obtain the acceptability with respect to $S \cup \{\alpha\}$ while in [5] it is with respect to S . Lemma 3 adapts Lemma 36 of [5]: the first two conditions of the statement are essentially the same, with the difference that in [5] the existence of a defeat is derived, while the third condition is additional.

Lemma 3. *Suppose β attacks α on α' according to Definition 11 and if α and β are defined as in Definition 9 then $Prem(\alpha) \cup Prem(\beta)$ is c-consistent. If $(\beta, \alpha) \notin D$ then one of the following conditions holds:*

1. $PDS_{AT}(\alpha' \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$;
2. *for some $\beta' \in M(\beta)$ there is a strict continuation $\alpha_{\beta'}^+$ of $(M(\beta) \setminus \{\beta'\}) \cup M(\alpha')$ such that $PDS_{AT}(\alpha_{\beta'}^+ \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$;*
3. $(\alpha, \beta) \in D$.

Proof. Given that β attacks α on α' according to Definition 11 but $(\beta, \alpha) \notin D$ there are two possible cases: i) the attack is not successful according to Definition 13, hence $PDS_{AT}(\beta \rightarrow \alpha) = \emptyset$, which implies $(\beta, \alpha) \notin D$ by Definition 19; ii) the attack is successful, i.e. $PDS_{AT}(\beta \rightarrow \alpha) \neq \emptyset$, but $(\beta, \alpha) \notin D$ i.e. $DGF_{AT}(\beta, \alpha) = F$. In the case ii)

from Definition 19 we get that it must be the case that $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$ and that $DGF_{AT}(\alpha, \beta) = \top$, hence $(\alpha, \beta) \in D$. Turning back to the case i) since the attack of β to α on α' is not successful, it must be the case that either β rebuts α' , i.e. α' has a defeasible top rule and $Conc(\beta) \in \overline{\varphi}$ where $\varphi = Conc(\alpha')$ or β undermines the ordinary premise $\alpha' = \varphi$. In both cases, it must hold that $Conc(\beta)$ is a contradictory of φ and $\beta \prec \alpha'$. From $\beta \prec \alpha'$ and Definition 12 it follows that β is not firm and strict. If β is an ordinary premise or has a defeasible top rule, we get that α' successfully undermines or rebuts β , hence $PDS_{AT}(\alpha' \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$. If β has a strict top rule the fact that for some $\beta' \in M(\beta)$ there is a strict continuation $\alpha_{\beta'}^+$ of $(M(\beta) \setminus \{\beta'\}) \cup M(\alpha')$ such that $PDS_{AT}(\alpha_{\beta'}^+ \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$ follows from Proposition 1. \square

Lemma 4 is analogous to Lemma 37 of [5] with the difference that we prove acceptability with respect to $E \cup \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$ rather than with respect to E as in [5].

Lemma 4. *Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a (c-)SAF, $\alpha \in S_A$ be a strict continuation of $\{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\} \subseteq S_A$ and for $i = 1, \dots, n$ α_i is acceptable with respect to $E \subseteq S_A$. Then α is acceptable with respect to $E \cup \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$.*

Proof. Consider any β such that $(\beta, \alpha) \in D$: by Definition 19 it must be the case that $PDS_{AT}(\beta \rightarrow \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. Hence there is $\langle \beta, \alpha, \alpha', T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some $\alpha' \in Sub(\alpha)$ and some attack type T . Since α is a strict continuation of $\{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$, in virtue of Definition 11, it must be the case that $\alpha' \in Sub(\alpha_i)$ for some $1 \leq i \leq n$. Hence there is $\langle \beta, \alpha_i, \alpha', T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ (note that it can be the case that $\alpha' = \alpha_i$) and we get that there is some $1 \leq i \leq n$ such that $PDS_{AT}(\beta \rightarrow \alpha_i) \neq \emptyset$. From Definition 19 it follows that $(\beta, \alpha_i) \in D$ or $(\alpha_i, \beta) \in D$. In the first case, since α_i is acceptable with respect to E there must be some $\gamma \in E$ which defends α_i , i.e. such that $(\gamma, \beta) \in D$. Hence γ defends also α from the attack of β . In the second case, it is α_i which defends α from the attack of β . Combining the conditions above, it follows that α is acceptable with respect to $E \cup \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$. \square

Proposition 2 obtains the same result as Proposition 9 of [5] with a slight difference in the hypotheses (we require admissibility of E rather than just conflict-freeness).

Proposition 2. *Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a c-SAF. If $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n$ are acceptable with respect to some admissible set $E \subseteq S_A$ then $\bigcup_{i=1}^n Prem(\alpha_i)$ is c-consistent.*

Proof. First we observe that it cannot be the case that there are $\varphi_1, \varphi_2 \in \bigcup_{i=1}^n Prem(\alpha_i)$ such that $\varphi_1 \in \overline{\varphi_2}$. This would imply that either φ_1 successfully attacks φ_2 or φ_2 successfully attacks φ_1 , i.e. $PDS_{AT}(\varphi_1 \rightarrow \varphi_2) \cup PDS_{AT}(\varphi_2 \rightarrow \varphi_1) \neq \emptyset$ from which it follows that $\{(\varphi_1, \varphi_2), (\varphi_2, \varphi_1)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. Suppose $(\varphi_1, \varphi_2) \in D$ (the other case is analogous). Then there is some α_i such that $\varphi_2 \in Prem(\alpha_i)$ and $PDS_{AT}(\varphi_1 \rightarrow \alpha_i) \neq \emptyset$. It follows that either i) $(\varphi_1, \alpha_i) \in D$ or ii) $(\alpha_i, \varphi_1) \in D$.

In the case i) it follows from the acceptability of α_i with respect to E that $\exists \gamma \in E$ such that $(\gamma, \varphi_1) \in D$. Hence $\exists \langle \gamma, \varphi_1, \varphi_1, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some attack type T . It follows that there is some α_j such that $\varphi_1 \in Prem_p(\alpha_j)$ for which it holds that $\exists \langle \gamma, \alpha_j, \varphi_1, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$, hence $PDS_{AT}(\gamma \rightarrow \alpha_j) \neq \emptyset$ from which it follows that $\{(\gamma, \alpha_j), (\alpha_j, \gamma)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. If $(\gamma, \alpha_j) \in D$ from the acceptability of α_j with respect to E it follows that $\exists \delta \in E$ such that $(\delta, \gamma) \in D$ contradicting (by Lemma 1) the att-conflict-freeness of E . If $(\alpha_j, \gamma) \in D$ from the admissibility of E it follows that $\exists \delta \in E$ such that $(\delta, \alpha_j) \in D$, from which, as above, we get a contradiction to the att-conflict-freeness of E .

In the case ii), from $(\alpha_i, \varphi_1) \in D$ we get that $\exists \langle \alpha_i, \varphi_1, \varphi_1, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some attack type T . Similarly to above, it follows that there is some α_j such that $\varphi_1 \in Prem_p(\alpha_j)$ for which it holds that $\exists \langle \alpha_i, \alpha_j, \varphi_1, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$, hence $PDS_{AT}(\alpha_i \rightarrow \alpha_j) \neq \emptyset$ from which it follows that $\{(\alpha_i, \alpha_j), (\alpha_j, \alpha_i)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. If $(\alpha_i, \alpha_j) \in D$ (the other case is analogous) from the acceptability of α_i with respect to E it follows that $\exists \gamma \in E$ such that $(\gamma, \alpha_i) \in D$. But then, from the acceptability of α_i with respect to E it follows that $\exists \delta \in E$ such that $(\delta, \gamma) \in D$ contradicting again the att-conflict-freeness of E .

Having proved this preliminary result, let us move to the main part of the proof. Suppose by contradiction that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n Prem(\alpha_i)$ is not c-consistent and let S be any minimally c-inconsistent subset of $\bigcup_{i=1}^n Prem(\alpha_i)$. By the assumption of c-classicality, we have that $\forall \varphi \in S$ it holds that $S \setminus \{\varphi\} \vdash \neg \varphi$ and $S \setminus \{\varphi\}$ is c-consistent. Now consider the set $S' = S \cap Prem_p(AT)$. By the assumption of axiom consistency, it must be the case that $S' \neq \emptyset$, i.e. $S' = \{\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_m\}$ with $m \geq 1$. Then we get that for every $1 \leq j \leq m$ there is a strict continuation $\beta^{+\setminus j}$ of $S' \setminus \{\varphi_j\}$ such that $Conc(\beta^{+\setminus j}) = \neg \varphi_j$, hence $\beta^{+\setminus j}$ undermines φ_j . Now, if S' is a singleton, we get that $\beta^{+\setminus j}$ is strict and firm and hence successfully undermines φ_j (with $j = 1$). Otherwise, from the hypothesis that \preceq is reasonable, we have that for some j $\beta^{+\setminus j} \not\prec \varphi_j$ and hence $\beta^{+\setminus j}$ successfully undermines φ_j . In any case, we have that there is $1 \leq j \leq m$ such that $\exists \langle \beta^{+\setminus j}, \varphi_j, \varphi_j, SM \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$. Observe now that since $\beta^{+\setminus j}$ is a strict continuation of $S' \setminus \{\varphi_j\}$, i.e. of $\{\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_{j-1}, \varphi_{j+1}, \dots, \varphi_m\}$, according to Definition 11, it can only be attacked on some element φ_k with $k \neq j$. As shown in the first part of the proof, it cannot be the case that there are $\varphi', \varphi'' \in \bigcup_{i=1}^n Prem(\alpha_i)$ such that $\varphi' \in \overline{\varphi''}$. It follows in particular that $\varphi_j \notin \overline{\varphi_k}$ with $k \neq j$, and hence φ_j cannot attack $\beta^{+\setminus j}$, i.e. $\nexists \langle \varphi_j, \beta^{+\setminus j}, \varphi_k, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$, for any $\varphi_k \in S'$ and any attack type T . Hence we get that $PDS_{AT}(\beta^{+\setminus j} \rightarrow \varphi_j) \neq \emptyset$ and $PDS_{AT}(\varphi_j \rightarrow \beta^{+\setminus j}) = \emptyset$, from which, by faithfulness, it follows $(\beta^{+\setminus j}, \varphi_j) \in D$.

Now, since every α_i , with $1 \leq i \leq n$, is acceptable with respect to E , from Lemma 2.4 we get in particular that φ_j is acceptable with respect to $E \cup \{\alpha_j\}$ for some α_j such that $\varphi_j \in Prem(\alpha_j)$. Hence there must be some $\gamma \in E \cup \{\alpha_j\}$ such that $(\gamma, \beta^{+\setminus j}) \in D$. As already noted, $\beta^{+\setminus j}$ can only be attacked on its ordinary premises, hence there must exist $\langle \gamma, \beta^{+\setminus j}, \varphi_k, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some $\varphi_k \in Prem_p(\beta^{+\setminus j})$ and some attack type T . Note that if $Prem_p(\beta^{+\setminus j}) = \emptyset$ we already get a contradiction, hence in the following we can assume $Prem_p(\beta^{+\setminus j}) \neq \emptyset$. From $\langle \gamma, \beta^{+\setminus j}, \varphi_k, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ we get also $\langle \gamma, \varphi_k, \varphi_k, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ from which we get also that $\langle \gamma, \alpha_l, \varphi_k, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some α_l , $1 \leq l \leq n$ such that $\varphi_k \in Prem_p(\alpha_l)$. It follows $PDS_{AT}(\gamma \rightarrow \alpha_l) \neq \emptyset$ and hence $(\gamma, \alpha_l), (\alpha_l, \gamma) \cap D \neq \emptyset$.

Suppose now first $\gamma = \alpha_j$: given that both α_j and α_l are acceptable with respect to E this would lead to contradict the att-conflict-freeness of E , as already seen in the first part of the proof.

We must therefore suppose that $\gamma \in E$. If $(\gamma, \alpha_l) \in D$ from the acceptability of α_l with respect to E we get that $\exists \delta \in E$ such that $(\delta, \gamma) \in D$ contradicting the att-conflict-freeness of E . If instead $(\alpha_l, \gamma) \in D$ from the admissibility of E it follows that $\exists \delta \in E$ such that $(\delta, \alpha_l) \in D$, from which, as above, we get in turn that $\exists \varepsilon \in E$ such that $(\varepsilon, \delta) \in D$ and then a contradiction to the att-conflict-freeness of E , concluding the proof. \square

Propositions 3 and 4 obtain the same results as Proposition 10 and 11 of [5].

Proposition 3. *Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a (c-)SAF. If α is acceptable with respect to some admissible set $E \subseteq S_A$ then $E' = E \cup \{\alpha\}$ is att-conflict-free.*

Proof. First note that by Proposition 2 if Δ is a *c-SAF*, for any $\beta \in E$, $Prem(\alpha) \cup Prem(\beta)$ is *c-consistent*. Assume by contradiction that E' is not att-conflict-free. By hypothesis, E is att-conflict-free, since it is admissible. Moreover it cannot be the case that $(\alpha, \alpha) \in D$ since a self-defeating argument cannot be acceptable with respect to any set and then $(\alpha, \alpha) \notin D$ implies that $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \alpha) = \emptyset$ which in turn implies that α does not attack α according to Definition 11. There are therefore only two possibilities for E' not being att-conflict-free:

- A. $\exists \beta \in E$ such that β attacks α while $(\beta, \alpha) \notin D$
- B. $\exists \beta \in E$ such that α attacks β while $(\alpha, \beta) \notin D$

Let us consider these two subcases.

Case A. Let β attack α on $\alpha' \in Sub(\alpha)$ while $(\beta, \alpha) \notin D$. From Lemma 3 we get that there are three possible subcases, each leading to a contradiction as shown in the following.

Case A.1: $PDS_{AT}(\alpha' \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$. It follows that $\{(\alpha', \beta), (\beta, \alpha')\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$.

If $(\alpha', \beta) \in D$, by admissibility of E there must be $\gamma \in E$ such that $(\gamma, \alpha') \in D$. From Lemma 2.3 we get $\{(\gamma, \alpha), (\alpha, \gamma)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. If $(\gamma, \alpha) \in D$, by the acceptability of α with respect to E we get that there is $\delta \in E$ such that $(\delta, \gamma) \in D$. However this contradicts $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$, which follows from the att-conflict-freeness of E by Lemma 1. If $(\alpha, \gamma) \in D$ by admissibility of E we get that there is $\delta \in E$ such that $(\delta, \alpha) \in D$, from which, as above, we get that there is $\varepsilon \in E$ such that $(\varepsilon, \delta) \in D$ contradicting $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$.

If in turn we assume $(\beta, \alpha') \in D$, we get a contradiction as from $(\gamma, \alpha') \in D$ above.

Case A.2: for some $\beta' \in M(\beta)$ there is a strict continuation $\alpha_{\beta'}^{'+}$ of $(M(\beta) \setminus \{\beta'\}) \cup M(\alpha')$ such that $PDS_{AT}(\alpha_{\beta'}^{'+} \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$. It follows that $\{(\alpha_{\beta'}^{'+}, \beta), (\beta, \alpha_{\beta'}^{'+})\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$.

If $(\alpha_{\beta'}^{'+}, \beta) \in D$, by admissibility of E we get that there is $\gamma \in E$ such that $(\gamma, \alpha_{\beta'}^{'+}) \in D$. It follows $PDS_{AT}(\gamma \rightarrow \alpha_{\beta'}^{'+}) \neq \emptyset$, i.e. $\exists \langle \gamma, \alpha_{\beta'}^{'+}, \delta, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some attack type T and some $\delta \in Sub(\alpha) \cup Sub(\beta)$. It follows that also $\langle \gamma, \delta, \delta, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ and we get that $\{(\gamma, \delta), (\delta, \gamma)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. If $(\gamma, \delta) \in D$, from Lemma 2.3 we get that $\{(\gamma, \alpha), (\alpha, \gamma), (\gamma, \beta), (\beta, \gamma)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$ contradicting $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. If $(\delta, \gamma) \in D$ from acceptability of γ we get that there is $\varepsilon \in E$ such that $(\varepsilon, \delta) \in D$, which using Lemma 2.3 as above leads again to contradict $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$.

If $(\beta, \alpha_{\beta'}^{'+}) \in D$ we get that $PDS_{AT}(\beta \rightarrow \alpha_{\beta'}^{'+}) \neq \emptyset$, i.e. $\exists \langle \beta, \alpha_{\beta'}^{'+}, \delta, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some attack type T and some $\delta \in Sub(\alpha) \cup Sub(\beta)$. It follows that also $\langle \beta, \delta, \delta, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ and we get that $\{(\beta, \delta), (\delta, \beta)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. If $(\beta, \delta) \in D$, from Lemma 2.3 we get that $\{(\beta, \alpha), (\alpha, \beta), (\beta, \beta)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$ contradicting as above $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. If $(\delta, \beta) \in D$ from acceptability of β we get that there is $\varepsilon \in E$ such that $(\varepsilon, \delta) \in D$, which using Lemma 2.3 as above leads again to contradict $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$.

Case A.3: $(\alpha, \beta) \in D$ which gives rise to a contradiction analogously to the case $(\alpha, \gamma) \in D$ with $\gamma \in E$ considered in the Case A.1.

Case B. Let α attack β on $\beta' \in Sub(\beta)$ while $(\alpha, \beta) \notin D$. From Lemma 3 we get again that there are three possible subcases, each leading to a contradiction as shown in the following.

Case B.1: $PDS_{AT}(\beta' \rightarrow \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. It follows that $\{(\beta', \alpha), (\alpha, \beta')\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. If $(\beta', \alpha) \in D$, by acceptability of α with respect to E we get that there is $\gamma \in E$ such that $(\gamma, \beta') \in D$, from which, by Lemma 2.3, $\{(\gamma, \beta), (\beta, \gamma)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$, leading to contradict $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. If $(\alpha, \beta') \in D$, from Lemma 2.3 we get $\{(\alpha, \beta), (\beta, \alpha)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$ leading to a contradiction as shown in the proof of Case A.1.

Case B.2: for some $\alpha' \in M(\alpha)$ there is a strict continuation $\beta_{\alpha'}^+$ of $(M(\alpha) \setminus \{\alpha'\}) \cup M(\beta')$ such that $PDS_{AT}(\beta_{\alpha'}^+ \rightarrow \alpha) \neq \emptyset$: a contradiction can be derived as in Case A.2.

Case B.3: $(\beta, \alpha) \in D$ which gives rise to a contradiction analogously to the case $(\gamma, \alpha) \in D$ with $\gamma \in E$ considered in the Case A.1. \square

Proposition 4. *Let α, α' be acceptable with respect to an admissible extension E of a (c-)SAF $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$. Then: i) $E' = E \cup \{\alpha\}$ is admissible; ii) α' is acceptable with respect to E' .*

Proof. By Lemma 2.1 all arguments in E' are acceptable with respect to E' . By Proposition 3 E' is att-conflict-free. Hence E' is admissible, proving statement i). Then statement ii) follows directly from Lemma 2.1. \square

Theorem 2 proves subargument closure similarly to Theorem 12 of [5].

Theorem 2. *Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a (c-)SAF and E a complete extension of \mathcal{F}_Δ^{DGF} . Then for all $\alpha \in E$: if $\alpha' \in \text{Sub}(\alpha)$ then $\alpha' \in E$.*

Proof. By Lemma 2.4, α' is acceptable with respect to $E \cup \{\alpha\}$, i.e. is acceptable with respect to E since $\alpha \in E$. $E \cup \{\alpha'\}$ is att-conflict-free by Proposition 3. Then, since E is complete, $\alpha' \in E$. \square

Theorem 3 proves closure under strict rules similarly to Theorem 13 of [5].

Theorem 3. *Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a (c-)SAF and E a complete extension of \mathcal{F}_Δ^{DGF} . Then $\{\text{Conc}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in E\} = \text{Cl}_{\mathcal{R}_S}(\{\text{Conc}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in E\})$.*

Proof. It suffices to show that for any strict continuation β of any set $\{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\} \subseteq E$ it holds that $\beta \in E$. By Lemma 4, β is acceptable with respect to $E \cup \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\}$, i.e. β is acceptable with respect to E since $\{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n\} \subseteq E$. $E \cup \{\beta\}$ is att-conflict-free by Proposition 3. Then, since E is complete, $\beta \in E$. Note that if Δ is a (c-)SAF, Proposition 2 guarantees that the premises of β are c-consistent. \square

Theorem 4 proves the property of direct consistency similarly to Theorem 14 of [5].

Theorem 4. *Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a (c-)SAF and E an admissible extension of \mathcal{F}_Δ^{DGF} . Then, $\{\text{Conc}(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in E\}$ is consistent.*

Proof. Suppose that there are $\alpha, \beta \in E$ such that $\text{Conc}(\alpha) \in \overline{\text{Conc}(\beta)}$: there are three cases (with relevant subcases) to consider, all leading to a contradiction.

Case 1. α is firm and strict. We have the following subcases. *Case 1.1:* β is also firm and strict: this would contradict the assumption of axiom consistency. *Case 1.2:* β is an ordinary premise or has a defeasible top rule. It follows that $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \neq \emptyset$ from which (taking into account that α cannot be attacked) we get $(\alpha, \beta) \in D$ which contradicts $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_\Delta^{DGF})$, which is implied by Lemma 1. *Case 1.3:* β is plausible or defeasible and has a strict top rule: covered by Case 3 in the following.

Case 2. α is plausible or defeasible. We have the following subcases. *Case 2.1:* β is firm and strict. It follows from the well-formedness assumption that $\text{Conc}(\alpha)$ and $\text{Conc}(\beta)$ are contradictory i.e. also $\text{Conc}(\beta) \in \text{Conc}(\alpha)$. In turn there are two sub-subcases. *Case 2.1.1:* α is an ordinary premise or has a defeasible top rule. Then $PDS_{AT}(\beta \rightarrow \alpha) \neq \emptyset$ from which (taking into account that β cannot be attacked) we get

$(\beta, \alpha) \in D$ which contradicts $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. *Case 2.1.2:* α has a strict top rule: covered by Case 3 in the following. *Case 2.2:* β is plausible or defeasible. In turn there are two subcases. *Case 2.2.1:* β is an ordinary premise or has a defeasible top rule. Then $PDS_{AT}(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \cup PDS_{AT}(\beta \rightarrow \alpha) \neq \emptyset$ from which we get $\{(\alpha, \beta), (\beta, \alpha)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$ which contradicts $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. *Case 2.2.2:* β has a strict top rule: covered by Case 3 in the following.

Case 3. This covers several cases mentioned above with $\gamma, \delta \in E$, $Conc(\gamma) \in \overline{Conc(\delta)}$, δ is defeasible or plausible and has a strict top rule. It follows from the well-formedness assumption that $Conc(\gamma)$ and $Conc(\delta)$ are contradictory i.e. also $Conc(\delta) \in \overline{Conc(\gamma)}$. Note that if Δ is a *c-SAF*, since γ and δ , being members of E , are acceptable with respect to E we get from Proposition 2 that $Prem(\gamma) \cup Prem(\delta)$ is c-consistent. By Proposition 1, for every $\delta' \in M(\delta)$ there exists a strict continuation $\gamma_{\delta'}^+$ of $(M(\delta) \setminus \{\delta'\}) \cup M(\gamma)$ such that $\gamma_{\delta'}^+$ rebuts or undermines δ on δ' , hence $PDS_{AT}(\gamma_{\delta'}^+ \rightarrow \delta) \cup PDS_{AT}(\delta \rightarrow \gamma_{\delta'}^+) \neq \emptyset$ and we get $\{(\gamma_{\delta'}^+, \delta), (\delta, \gamma_{\delta'}^+)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. However, taking into account that $M(\delta) \cup M(\gamma) \subseteq E$ by Theorem 2, from Lemma 4 we get that $\gamma_{\delta'}^+$ is acceptable with respect to E . By Proposition 3, $\gamma_{\delta'}^+ \cup E$ is att-conflict-free and, by Lemma 1, $\gamma_{\delta'}^+ \cup E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. Since $\delta \in E$ and $\{(\gamma_{\delta'}^+, \delta), (\delta, \gamma_{\delta'}^+)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$, we get a contradiction. \square

As in [5], the final result on indirect consistency is a straightforward consequence.

Theorem 5. *Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a (c-)SAF and E a complete extension of $\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF}$. Then $Cl_{\mathcal{R}_s}(\{Conc(\alpha) \mid \alpha \in E\})$ is consistent.*

Proof. Follows directly from Theorems 3 and 4. \square

Having achieved the above result, it is finally worth remarking (similarly to section 4.3 of [5]) that using the ‘conventional’ notion of conflict-freeness based on the relation D would be equivalent. First of all, we note that Proposition 1, and Lemmas 2, 3 and 4 do not use the notion of conflict-freeness. The proof of Proposition 2 resorts to contradiction of att-conflict-freeness by showing the existence of defeats in D and hence holds anyway.

Propositions 3 and 4 reproduce, under att-conflict-freeness, well-known results proved in [4] for ‘conventional’ conflict-freeness and hence Theorems 2 and 3 hold under both notions. Theorem 4, similarly to Proposition 2, resorts to contradictions derived from defeats in D . Then also Theorem 5 obviously holds.

It remains only to show that the notion of admissibility is equivalent under the two alternative notions of conflict-freeness, which is shown by Proposition 5.

Proposition 5. *Let $\Delta = (S_A, C, \preceq)$ be a (c-)SAF and $\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF}$ be the relevant argumentation framework. A set $E \subseteq S_A$ is att-conflict-free and such that $E \subseteq F_{\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF}}(E)$ if and only if $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$ and $E \subseteq F_{\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF}}(E)$.*

Proof. We need to prove that a set E such that $E \subseteq F_{\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF}}(E)$ is att-conflict-free if and only if $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. Let us assume att-conflict-freeness first: then $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$ follows from Lemma 1. Conversely, assume now $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$ and suppose by contradiction that there are $\alpha, \beta \in E$ such that α attacks β on some $\beta' \in Sub(\beta)$ according to Definition 11. First, note that since α and β are acceptable with respect to E , in the

case of a *c-SAF* by Proposition 2 $Prem(\alpha) \cup Prem(\beta)$ is *c-consistent*. Then by Lemma 3 there are three possible cases, all leading to a contradiction.

Case 1. $PDS_{AT}(\beta' \rightarrow \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. From faithfulness it follows that $\{(\beta', \alpha), (\alpha, \beta')\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. If $(\beta', \alpha) \in D$ from acceptability of α we get that there is $\gamma \in E$ such that $(\gamma, \beta') \in D$. From Lemma 2.3 we get $\{(\beta, \gamma), (\gamma, \beta)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$ contradicting $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. If $(\alpha, \beta') \in D$ similarly we get from Lemma 2.3 that $\{(\alpha, \beta), (\beta, \alpha)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$ contradicting $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$.

Case 2. for some $\alpha' \in M(\alpha)$ there is a strict continuation $\beta_{\alpha'}^{'+}$ of $(M(\alpha) \setminus \{\alpha'\}) \cup M(\beta')$ such that $PDS_{AT}(\beta_{\alpha'}^{'+} \rightarrow \alpha) \neq \emptyset$. By acceptability of α there is $\gamma \in E$ such that $(\gamma, \beta_{\alpha'}^{'+}) \in D$. It follows $PDS_{AT}(\gamma \rightarrow \beta_{\alpha'}^{'+}) \neq \emptyset$, i.e. $\exists \langle \gamma, \beta_{\alpha'}^{'+}, \delta, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ for some attack type T and some $\delta \in Sub(\alpha) \cup Sub(\beta)$. It follows that also $\langle \gamma, \delta, \delta, T \rangle \in PDS_{AT}$ and we get that $\{(\gamma, \delta), (\delta, \gamma)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$. If $(\gamma, \delta) \in D$, from Lemma 2.3 we get that $\{(\gamma, \alpha), (\alpha, \gamma), (\gamma, \beta), (\beta, \gamma)\} \cap D \neq \emptyset$ contradicting $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. If $(\delta, \gamma) \in D$ from acceptability of γ we get that there is $\varepsilon \in E$ such that $(\varepsilon, \delta) \in D$, which using Lemma 2.3 as above leads again to contradict $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$.

Case 3. $(\beta, \alpha) \in D$. This directly contradicts $E \in \mathcal{E}_{CF}(\mathcal{F}_{\Delta}^{DGF})$. \square

From the equivalence of the notion of admissibility it follows immediately that all other semantics notions, whose definition relies on admissibility, are also equivalent.

5. Conclusions

We discussed polymorphic attacks, namely cases where an argument attacks another one in more than one way, evidencing that they can occur in some practical reasoning context. While *ASPIC⁺* has a sort of default strategy to deal with polymorphic attacks, we proposed an explicit and more flexible management, based on the notion of defeat generation function, and we proved that any defeat generation function satisfying a property of faithfulness ensures the respect of the rationality postulates of [3]. Among the directions of future work we mention a broader analysis of practical situations where polymorphic attacks occur, the investigation of alternative instances of defeat generation function, and the study of polymorphic attacks in other structured argumentation formalisms.

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